

FACE MASK DETECTION USING CNN VGG16 MODEL WITH IMPROVED ACCURACY

By Sirat Singh Anand

Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Email: sirat2711@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

With the outbreak of the Coronavirus Disease in 2019, life seemed to be had come to a standstill. To combat the transmission of the virus, World Health Organization (WHO) announced wearing of face mask as an imperative way to limit the spread of the virus. However, manually ensuring whether people are wearing face masks or not in a public area is a cumbersome task. The exigency of monitoring people wearing face masks necessitated building an automatic system. This paper provides a simple way to detect whether a person is wearing a face mask or not by utilising some fundamental machine learning tools such as TensorFlow, Keras, OpenCV and Scikit-Learn. The system consists of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture capable of detecting masked and unmasked faces and it can be integrated with pre-installed CCTV cameras. This would help to track safety violations, promote the use of face masks, and ensure a safe working environment. Furthermore, the pros and cons of the proposed method has been discussed and we also investigate the optimal parameter values for the Convolutional Neural Network model (CNN) to identify the existence of masks accurately without generating over-fitting.

Keywords: Coronavirus Disease 2019 • Face mask detection • CNN • TensorFlow • Keras • OpenCV

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) research has advanced significantly in recent years, especially in the area of machine learning. Without AI it is very difficult nowadays to make any significant progress in terms of technical innovation. AI is being considered as the next big thing that will change the world tremendously. Modern Computer Vision algorithms are approaching human-level performance in visual perception tasks. From image classification to video analytics, Computer Vision has proven to be a revolutionary aspect of modern technology. In a world battling against the Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic, technology has been a lifesaver.

As the pandemic slowly settles and such sectors become eager to resume in-person work, individuals are still sceptical of getting back to the office. Multiple studies have shown that the use of face masks reduces the risk of viral transmission as well as provides a sense of protection. However, it is infeasible to manually enforce such policy on large scale and track any violations. Computer vision provides a better alternative to this. Using a combination of image classification, object detection, object tracking and video analysis, I have developed a robust system that can detect the presence and absence of face masks in images as well as videos.

In this paper, I propose a CNN architecture where the model detects the human face first and then classifies the face as either 'Mask' or 'No Mask' faces and draws bounding boxes around them along with detected class name. This algorithm was further extended to videos as well. The detected faces are then tracked between frames using an object tracking algorithm, which makes the detection robust to the noise due to motion blur. This system can be integrated with an image or video capturing device like a CCTV camera, to a track safety violation, promote the use of face masks, and ensure safe working environment.

CNN VGG16 is a clever neural network used for doing object detection in real-time. It becomes very difficult to train these models, keeping in mind the diversity of camera angles in images and mask types, so this issue pops out as a challenge for me. Another challenge I faced was the unavailability of a large dataset for training the two categories – one with mask and second without mask, so the authors have made a custom dataset and used transfer learning to achieve this task.

1.1 Motivation

With time, the surge in COVID-19 cases urged people to be cautious, alert, and take all safety measures possible. In situations such as this, where a mere sneeze could be harmful to many people, safety remains the priority. To ensure the well-being of all humans, a system that could itself monitor if a face mask is on or not is required. It would not only secure a being rather fellows in the vicinity as well. Having access to the ultra-modern technological methods, implementing such a system could be a boon to society.

Several already existing datasets were explored, along with the techniques available. The literature survey of the available methods was conducted, followed by a comparison of different algorithms. Further, the software was explored and thereby applications. Initially, around 190 papers were identified belonging to varied publications like Springer, Zenodo.org etc. Later, the collected documents were checked for duplication and removed, further the papers were assessed for quality, bringing down the count to 150. Few more publications were analysed to gather the knowledge about the available datasets.

Figure 1: Methodology flowchart

The above diagram illustrates the methodology and the steps conducted.

2. METHOD

2.1 Related Work:

Traditional Object Detection – The problem of detecting multiple masked and unmasked faces in images can be solved by a traditional object detection model. The process of object detection mainly involves localizing the objects in images and classifying them (in case of multiple objects). Traditional algorithms such as Haar Cascade and HOG have proved to be effective for such tasks, but these algorithms are heavily based on Feature Engineering. In the era of deep learning, it is possible to train Neural Networks that outperform these algorithms and do not need any extra Feature engineering.

Convolutional Neural Networks – CNN is a key aspect in modern Computer Vision tasks like pattern object detection, image classification, pattern recognition tasks, etc. A CNN uses convolutional kernels to convolve with the original images or feature maps to extract higher-level features, thus resulting in a very powerful tool for Computer Vision tasks.

Face Mask Detection: As the world began implementing precautionary measures against the Coronavirus, numerous implementations of face mask detection system came forth. However, most of the models have an accuracy of around 80% and not more than that. Few of the related works are listed below –

1. (Qin and Li, 2020) introduced a method to identify face mask wearing conditions. They divided the facemask wearing conditions into three categories: correct face mask wearing, incorrect face mask wearing, and no face mask wearing. Their system takes an image, detects and crops faces, and then uses SRCNet (Dong et al., 2016) to perform image super-resolution and classify them.

2. The work by (Nieto-Rodríguez et al., 2015) presented a method that detects the presence or absence of a medical mask. The primary objective of this approach was to trigger an alert only for medical staff who do not wear a surgical mask, by minimizing as many false- positive face detections as possible, without missing any medical mask detections.

3. (Loey et al., 2021) proposed a model that consists of two components. The first component performs uses ResNet50 (He et al., 2016) for feature extraction. The next component is a facemask classifier, based on an ensemble of classical Machine Learning algorithms. The authors evaluated their system and estimated that Deep Transfer Learning approaches would achieve better results since the building, comparing, and selecting the best model among a set of classical Machine Learning models is a time-consuming process.

2.2 Proposed methodology

The implementation of the face mask detection system can be executed in two phases.

The first phase is the training phase. This stage is initiated with the collection of the dataset. One of the most crucial steps is to have a good quantity and quality of data. One can prepare the dataset or use already existing datasets from the various available resources. If preparing yourself, the size of data could be increased by using techniques of data augmentation. Also, the data has to be cleaned before use because it plays a significant role in building a model. Various steps involved in data cleaning are shown below –

Figure 2: Flow diagram for face mask detection system

After obtaining a good quality dataset, the model is selected under the system's demands and trained on the chosen dataset. Multiple techniques could be used to accomplish the target. By acquiring the most suitable trained model, the first phase comes to an end. In the subsequent steps, the frames from live video feed or the images are used to input to the trained model. Image pre-processing is also needed because sometimes the video inputs could be blurred or not clear. We can also use object tracking to detect faces.

The implementation of the project is carried out in python notebook. Libraries like pandas, NumPy, matplotlib, sklearn etc are used. To train the CNN model and to run the python code for the project the following libraries are required – TensorFlow, Keras, NumPy, OpenCV. The two phases of the face mask detection implementation are explained below:

1. Training – We will collect our facial mask detection record of a hard drive to form a model (with keras / TensorFlow) and finally serialize the facial mask detector on the disk.
2. Deployment – After the face mask detector has been trained, we charge the mask detector, perform face recognition, and then decide whether each face is equipped with or without a mask. Also, it will require a webcam.

The below diagram represents the steps in building the CNN model –

Figure 3: Steps in building the CNN model.

2.3 Datasets

The final dataset has 841 images, divided into two classes.

Class Name	Description	No. of images
Mask	Images with faces having masks	422
No_mask	Images with faces not having masks	419

The dataset used in this project is a face dataset (with/without mask dataset) taken from roboflow.com.

Dataset is the major part for building the CNN model. More number of images the dataset has, the more accurate the model will be.

2.4 Process flow and CNN architecture

Figure 4: Process flow of data

Convolutional Neural Network – In deep learning, a CNN model is usually fed with an image as an input which is then made to pass through multiple layers. To begin with, the input is made to pass through convolutional layers with kernels in succession, followed by a pooling layer. This layer then reduces the number of learning parameters and hence computations by turning down the size of feature maps. It is afterwards carried through fully connected layers, which at the end apply a SoftMax function that predicts the probabilistic values for each class. The class having the maximum value is then taken to be the class to which the object belongs. CNN can make use of varied backbone architectures to achieve the task. In the VGG-16 architecture of CNN is discussed. Convolutional Neural Networks are a class of deep learning models specifically designed for processing structured grid-like data, such as images or time series data. They have been widely used and highly successful in various computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and image segmentation. The key feature of Convolutional Neural Networks is the convolutional layer. This layer applies a set of learnable filters, also known as kernels or feature detectors, to the input data. The filters scan the input data using a sliding window technique, performing element-wise multiplication and summation to produce a feature map. The convolutional layer's purpose is to capture local patterns and spatial hierarchies present in the input data. Convolutional Neural Networks typically consist of multiple convolutional layers, interspersed with pooling layers and followed by one or more fully connected layers. Pooling layers reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, helping to extract dominant features while providing a degree of translation invariance. Fully connected layers take the high-level features extracted by the preceding layers and perform classification or regression tasks. During training, Convolutional Neural Networks optimize their parameters through a process called backpropagation. This involves feeding training examples through the network, computing the loss between the predicted outputs and the true labels, and adjusting the weights of the network using gradient descent. The goal is to minimize the loss function and improve the network's ability to generalize to unseen data. Convolutional Neural Networks have revolutionized the field of computer vision by achieving state-of-the-art results on various benchmark datasets. Their ability to automatically learn hierarchical representations from raw input data has made them indispensable in tasks such as image recognition, object detection, and even tasks beyond computer vision, such as natural language processing and drug discovery.

VGG16 model - VGG16, or Visual Geometry Group 16, refers to a specific convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture that was developed by the Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford. It gained popularity and became a benchmark model for image classification tasks. VGG16 consists of 16 layers, including 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. The key idea behind VGG16 is to use a series of smaller 3x3 convolutional filters stacked on top of each other, instead of larger filters, to capture and learn complex patterns

and features in an image. The architecture of VGG16 is characterized by its simplicity and uniformity. It maintains a consistent pattern of convolutional layers with 3x3 filters and max-pooling layers throughout the network. The number 16 in VGG16 refers to the total number of weight layers in the network. VGG16 achieved impressive performance on image classification tasks, particularly in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) in 2014. It demonstrated the effectiveness of deep convolutional neural networks in learning and representing high-level features from images, leading to improved accuracy in image recognition. VGG16 has been widely used as a pre-trained model for transfer learning. By leveraging the learned weights and feature representations from VGG16, researchers and practitioners can fine-tune the model for their specific image classification tasks, even with limited amounts of data.

The formula (softmax function) for the VGG16 model is given below –

$$P(y=j \mid \Theta^{(i)}) = \frac{e^{\Theta^{(i)}}}{\sum_{j=0}^k e^{\Theta_k^{(i)}}}$$

softmax function

where $\Theta = w_0x_0 + w_1x_1 + \dots + w_kx_k = \sum_{i=0}^k w_ix_i = w^T x$

Figure 5: CNN architecture

3. WORKING

3.1 Stage 1 – Face Detector: A face detector acts as the first stage of our system. A raw RGB image is passed as the input to this stage. The face detector extracts and outputs all the faces detected in the image with their bounding box coordinates. The process of detecting faces accurately is very important for our architecture. Training a highly accurate face detector needs a lot of labelled data, time and compute resources. For these reasons, we selected a pre trained model trained on a large dataset for easy generalization and stability in detection.

3.2 Intermediate Processing block - This block carries out the processing of the detected faces and batches them together for classification, which is carried out by Stage 2. The detector from stage 1 outputs the bounding boxes for the faces. Stage 2 requires the entire head of the person to accurately classify the faces as masked or unmasked. The first step involves expanding the bounding boxes in height and width by 20%, which covers the required region of interest (ROI) with minimal overlap with other faces in most situations. The second step involves cropping out the expanded bounding boxes from the image to extract the ROI for each detected face. The extracted faces are resized and normalized as required by stage 2. Furthermore, all the faces are batched together for batch interference.

3.3 Stage 2 – Face Mask Classifier: The second stage of our system is a face mask classifier. This stage takes the processed ROI from the intermediate processing block and classifies it as either Mask or No Mask. A CNN based classifier for this stage was trained, based on three different image classification models. These models have a lightweight architecture that offers high performance with low latency, which is suitable for video analysis. The output of this stage is an image (or video frame) with localized faces, classified as masked or unmasked.

4. TRAINING AND TESTING

Pseudocode –

Training:

1. Generate your own annotation file and class names file: Row Format: image_file_path box 1, box2, ... boxN. Box format: x_min, y_min, x_max, y_max, class_id

2. Convert the pre-trained weights to '.h5' format as required by Keras.
3. Freeze all layers except the final layers and train for some epochs until Plateau (no improvement stage) is reached.
4. Unfreeze all the layers and train all the weights while continuously reducing the learning rate until again plateau is reached.
5. End

Testing:

For testing we will be using 2 images – 1.jpg and 2.jpg as sample images. 1.jpg is masked and 2.jpg is unmasked.

```
In [38]: sample1 = cv2.imread('sample/1.jpg')
sample1 = cv2.resize(sample1,(224,224))

In [39]: test1 = detect_face_mask(sample1)
if test1 == 0:
    print("MASK DETECTED")
else:
    print("NO MASK DETECTED")

1/1 [=====] - 1s 1s/step
MASK DETECTED

In [40]: sample2 = cv2.imread('sample/2.jpg')
sample2 = cv2.resize(sample2,(224,224))

In [41]: test2 = detect_face_mask(sample2)
if test2 == 0:
    print("MASK DETECTED")
else:
    print("NO MASK DETECTED")

1/1 [=====] - 1s 654ms/step
NO MASK DETECTED
```

Figure 6

If the function detect_face_mask() returns the value 0 then it means that the mask has been detected in the image, and if the value 1 is returned then it means that no mask has been detected in the image.

4.1 Accuracy and loss

In order to train this model, I have used 5 epochs. In Machine Learning, an epoch is a complete iteration through a dataset during the training of a model. During each epoch, the model is presented with the entire training dataset,

and the model's weights and biases are updated in order to minimize error in the training data. The process of training a model typically involves multiple epochs, with each epoch improving the model's accuracy. In deep learning, models can have hundreds or thousands of epochs, each of which can take a significant time to complete, especially models that have hundreds or thousands of parameters.

The number of epochs used in the training process is an important hyperparameter that must be carefully selected, as too few epochs can result in an undertrained model, while too many epochs can result in overfitting, where the model becomes too specialized to the training data and performs poorly on new, unseen data.

Below is the table displaying the loss, accuracy, value loss and value accuracy –

EPOCH	LOSS	ACCURACY	VAL_LOSS	VAL_ACCURACY
1	0.3863	0.8467	0.1095	0.9586
2	0.0404	0.9836	0.0241	0.9941
3	0.0147	0.9955	0.0226	0.9882
4	0.0098	1.0000	0.0200	0.9941
5	0.0071	1.0000	0.0193	0.9941

As we can clearly see, epoch 4 and epoch 5 give the accuracy of 100% and with increasing number of epochs, the accuracy keeps on improving.

AVERAGE ACCURACY	0.96516
AVERAGE VALUE ACCURACY	0.98582

```
In [34]: model.compile(optimizer='Adam',loss='binary_crossentropy',metrics=['accuracy'])
In [35]: model.fit(X_train,Y_train,epochs=5,validation_data=(X_test,Y_test))
Epoch 1/5
21/21 [=====] - 391s 19s/step - loss: 0.3863 - accuracy: 0.8467 - val_loss: 0.1095 - val_accuracy: 0.9586
Epoch 2/5
21/21 [=====] - 2741s 137s/step - loss: 0.0404 - accuracy: 0.9836 - val_loss: 0.0241 - val_accuracy: 0.9941
Epoch 3/5
21/21 [=====] - 416s 20s/step - loss: 0.0147 - accuracy: 0.9955 - val_loss: 0.0226 - val_accuracy: 0.9882
Epoch 4/5
21/21 [=====] - 412s 20s/step - loss: 0.0098 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0200 - val_accuracy: 0.9941
Epoch 5/5
21/21 [=====] - 413s 20s/step - loss: 0.0071 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0193 - val_accuracy: 0.9941
Out[35]: <keras.callbacks.History at 0x20a0d9b29d0>
```

Figure 7

5. RESULT AND OUTPUTS

The results are more of what was expected of the model. The mask recognition is implemented using the camera as a medium and shows accurate results. When the person's face is in the camera frame, a model will show the face and a green or a red frame will appear over the face. The person who is not wearing the mask will get a red frame over his face in camera while the person who is wearing the mask will get a green frame. The result is also visible

written next to the resultant frame. The model works even if the side view of the face is visible to the camera. It can also detect more than one face in a single camera frame. Combining all the components of our architecture, we get a highly robust and accurate Face Mask Detection System. Overall, the model shows accurate results and exhibits high performance.

OUTPUTS – Below are the outputs of four different conditions – Wearing The mask, Not wearing the mask, Covering the mouth and nose with hand, Not properly covering the nose with mask respectively.

OUTPUT 1

OUTPUT 2

OUTPUT 3

OUTPUT 4

6. APPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This model has various applications and can be used at many places such as:

1. Transit Hubs: At places like airports, railway stations etc, face mask detectors with security cameras can be implemented to keep a check on travellers whether they are wearing the face mask or not. The passenger's face could be detected throughout the premises and the authorities could be informed immediately if any violation is detected.
2. Workplaces: A mechanism to observe if an employee has worn a face mask or not could be incorporated in an office. A warning message could be sent to people who are not following the safety precautions. Also, a daily record of people not complying with the regulations could be maintained.
3. Healthcare centres: In various healthcare organizations and hospitals, a face mask detection system could track healthcare workers wearing face masks during their shifts. Besides, it could be helpful in alerting

the visitors entering the premises without a face mask. The authorities could be immediately informed in case of defiance.

LIMITATIONS – Although the system performs efficiently in real time, it still faces a lot of challenges.

1. The irregularities in image, like those with insufficient light and side angle, need proper attention.
2. Motion blur, transitioning between frames causes a decrease in accuracy of the model.
3. Large dataset performance leads to limitations.

7. SCOPE

Even if several case studies have been enrolled to demonstrate the real-time scenario of the COVID-19 issue, the deployment of the systems in real-time is extremely difficult. Developing a system that is adaptive to all contexts and surroundings is becoming a difficulty. The proposed device might be deployed in high-traffic areas to keep a close eye on people. If we consider the cost estimation for implementing the project, it will be almost of no cost as most of the metropolitan cities already have cameras installed in public places. Camera, which is the only main requirement of the proposed model is already available. Our model is based on neural networks. A neural network is a network or circuit of neurons, which is also called an artificial neural network and is made up of artificial neurons or nodes. Some of the important types of neural networks are Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). Different fields including Math, Physics, and Neuroscience have all had an impact on Artificial Neural Networks. Neuroscience made a significant contribution to the original inspiration for Artificial Neural Networks. Consider the recent success of biologically inspired Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN).

- Learning Dynamic is the same as Cost Function Optimization in the brain.
- Task Specificity is required for both architectures and cost functions to reach a satisfactory level of performance.

These are some of the ANN inspired speculations in the Computational Neuroscience field. CNN is well versed in neuroscience field. To extract characteristics from MRI images, a CNN was used. CNN creates a link between medical and technology fields. The discipline of neuroscience informatics focuses on multidisciplinary, translational, and technological research that is fuelled by imaging. While in image and video processing tasks, CNN is extremely common. There is so much of scope for CNN in neuroscience informatics. The face mask recognition system, which is based on CNN model uses dataset consists of different facial images with and without mask. The same model can be used for different purposes related to image processing in neuroscience using dataset containing images related to that task.

8. CONCLUSION

Measures must be taken to control the spread of the COVID19 pandemic. This face mask recognition system is a very good and efficient way to do so. The system will separate the people from the crowd who are not wearing mask. The identification of people, violating the COVID norms increases the adaptability of the face mask detection system for the public sake. If applied in a correct way, the face mask detection system could be used to make sure our safety and for others too. This approach gives not only helps in achieving high precision but also enhance the face detection tempo considerably. The system can be applied in many areas like metro stations, markets, schools, railway stations and many other crowded places to monitor the crowd and to ensure that everyone is wearing mask. Finally, this work can be used for future researchers and enthusiasts. Firstly, this model can be used in any high-definition camcorders, this will make sure that this model is not limited to only face mask detection system. Secondly, this can be used for biometric scans with a mask on the face. In this paper, we made use of a CNN VGG16 model in order to classify the images and segregate them on the basis of “masked” and “unmasked”. With the world looking to return to normalcy and people resuming in-person work, this system can be easily deployed for automated monitoring of the use of face masks at workplaces, thus making the working environment much safer for the people.

9. FUTURE SCOPE

We plan to update the mask recognition system and announce it as an open-source project. This system can be implemented in these retail shops and the result can be seen on the digital and promotional screens. This app can be used with any current USB, IP, or CCTV cameras for identifying people who do not wear a mask. The live video mask detection function can be introduced in web and desktop applications so that the operator may know whether users are not wearing masks and warning messages can be lost. If anyone isn't wearing a mask, images should be submitted to software operators. Furthermore, we can mount an alarm device that will emit a beep sound if anyone enters the area without wearing a mask. Only people wearing face masks can enter using this software, which can be linked to the entrance gates. This system could be connected in hospital gates, schools, malls and at many more public places.

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GLOSSARY/APPENDIX

TensorFlow – It is an open-source machine learning framework developed by google. It provides a comprehensive ecosystem of tools for building complex ML models.

Keras – It is a high-level deep learning library written in python. It provides user-friendly interface to build and train neural networks.

OpenCV (Computer Vision) – It is a field of study that focuses on enabling computers to understand and interpret visual data, such as images and videos. It is used for object recognition, image classification etc.

CNN – Convolutional Neural Networks are a type of deep neural networks specifically designed for analyzing visual data. They employ convolutional layers to automatically learn patterns and features from images.

VGG16 – It refers to Visual Geometry Group 16 and is a specific type of CNN architecture. It is composed of 16 layers, including 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers.

NumPy – NumPy is short form for Numerical Python which is used for numerical computing.

Scikit-learn – Also known as sklearn is a widely used machine learning library in Python. It provides a comprehensive set of tools for various machine learning tasks, including data preprocessing, model selection and evaluation.

Kernel – A kernel refers to a small piece of software that acts as a bridge between the hardware and software applications running on a computer system.

Matplotlib – It is a widely used python library for creating high-quality data visualizations and plots. It provides flexible tools for generating histograms, scatter plots, bar charts etc.

Accuracy – It is a commonly used metric to evaluate the performance of a classification model. It represents the percentage of correct predictions made by the model on a given dataset.

Loss – It refers to a measure of how well a machine learning model is performing on a given task. It quantifies the discrepancy between the predicted output of the model and the actual or expected output.

Object detection – It is a computer vision task that involves identifying and localizing objects within digital images or videos.

Face mask detection system – It is a specific application of object detection that focuses on identifying whether individuals in images or video frames are wearing face masks or not. It helps in enforcing safety measures and compliance with mask-wearing guidelines.

Object classification – It is a computer vision task that involves assigning a label or category to an object within an image. It aims to determine what type of object is present in the image from a predefined set of classes.

Image Processing – It refers to the manipulation and analysis of digital images using computer algorithms. It involves various techniques to enhance, transform, or extract information from images.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Sirat Singh Anand born 27th November 2001 in Delhi, India is an undergraduate Engineering student currently pursuing *computer science engineering with cloud computing as program elective* in final year at Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

He has gained a great amount of experience by working upon several tasks in Internships, with work experience including:

- Web development remote internship starting June 2023, at WictroniX, a startup providing B2B IT services and consultations to established companies, launched in late 2022 and registered by the Government of India.
- Full stack developer remote internship at Simtrak solutions starting January 2023 till May 2023, another startup founded in 2020 that provides business and analytical solutions to other established companies.
- Machine Learning remote internship at Verzeo, joined in the year 2021, where the author worked with the tech team to perform Exploratory Data Analysis on the datasets provided.
- The author was also the member of the GDSC (Google Developer Students club), IEEE club and ACM club at Manipal University Jaipur.

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